

Elevated platforms in broiler chicken barns

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Context

Perching behaviour is essential for poultry welfare: birds perch to rest, self-preen and feel safe. Broilers will attempt to perch on any elevated structures (e.g., bales, perches, water pipes). However, only elevated platforms with ramps can be navigated and used comfortably by fast-growing broilers at all ages. Providing elevated platforms (Fig. 1) is a good practice to improve broiler welfare. These platforms support the birds in performing their natural resting behaviour, but also mitigate the occurrence of leg problems. Platforms are more suitable than perches for fast-growing broilers, as their larger surface area helps accommodate the birds' reduced mobility and poor balance, the latter being caused mainly by the large breast of the broiler.

Fig. 1: Use of elevated platform by broiler chickens.
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Background and challenges

Due to genetic selection and optimised diet, commercial broilers grow much faster nowadays than in the late 1950s (Fig. 2). The rapid growth and selection for large breast and thighs result in the broilers becoming

increasingly inactive with age. The fast growth has led to welfare problems in broilers, including leg disorders and bone deformations, causing leg weakness, impaired walking ability and extended periods spent sitting or lying, which can instigate footpad dermatitis and hock burns. Moreover, broilers are typically kept in low stimulus floor housing with only feed, water and litter provided. Some species-specific behaviour, such as perching, cannot be performed under these conditions.

Fig. 2: The broiler hybrids depicted are (left to right) from 1957, 1978 and 2005. They were all reared under the same conditions and photographed at the same age. Source: Zuidhof et al. (2014)¹ Licensed under CC-BY.

Benefits

Scientific literature^{2,3,4} suggests that providing elevated platforms to broilers have multiple welfare benefits. Elevated platforms not only provide additional locomotory possibilities for broilers and allow natural resting behaviour but are also known to reduce the prevalence and severity of lameness, dyschondroplasia, footpad dermatitis and hock burns⁵.

Furthermore, elevated platforms diversify the housing environment. In addition, the birds can use the space under the platform as a hiding place and thus feel safe. Furthermore, broilers resting on platforms have a better quality of rest, because they are less disturbed by active flock mates⁶.

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Recommendations

Broilers are highly motivated to use platforms from the first week of life. **The platforms should be incorporated into the farms before the arrival of the chicks and should be easily accessible to the birds at all ages.** Therefore, ramps (Fig. 1) should be provided in order to ease access (maximum slope: 25 degrees⁷).

Fig. 3: Elevated platform with adaptable height to the birds' size.
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A common practice is to allocate an elevated platform area that represents at least 1% of the building's total surface area (i.e., 10 m² of perching area for a 1000 m² building). The size is approximately 3 m × 0.70 m, and the ratio is 0.3 m²/ 1000 chickens. However, the **evidence of the optimal surface area of the platforms per bird and the optimal design is still lacking.**

Platforms can vary in the material used, length, height, etc. (Fig. 3). Typically, the platforms are made of plastic slats, which may be reused slats from laying hen farms. While platforms are heavier to move and more expensive than straw bales, they can nevertheless accommodate a larger number of birds and the investment is a one-off purchase. Cleaning time should be considered, but winches, although more expensive, eliminate the need to carry platforms and make cleaning easier (Fig. 4). A transport cart can also help in transporting the platforms (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4: Platforms raised thanks to winches for easy handling and cleaning ©michard-aviculture.com

Fig.5: A transport cart to simplify the handling of the platforms
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References

This Good practice has also been identified in the EU Broilernet network: <https://broilernet.eu/>

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